

“Financing Start-ups: A changing trend in India.”

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Abstract

Finance is a predominant factor for the growth and development of a company. India is becoming a start-up hub. Opportunity for growth is extensive. Start-up in India has increased gradually taking a total number to 7200 start-ups in 2018 alone and holds the position as the third largest start-up ecosystem. Indian start-ups have come of age and they are building products for the global spectators. Start-up companies are newly founded companies or entrepreneurial venture that are based on transformation, expansion and market research which struggle for existence. Start-ups are the life blood of our economy, they create employment opportunities, new products and disruption too. Our study focuses on understanding the concept and how start-ups in India are being funded by Investment agencies specifically by Angel Investors, Crowd funding and Venture capital. The research also provides an insight of how they play a major role in aiding the start-ups to contribute for the development of the Indian economy. This study is purely based on secondary information.

Key words: Start-ups, Financing, Funding, Angel Investors, Crowd Funding, Venture capital.

INTRODUCTION

A startup is a budding company that is just beginning to develop. Startups are initially financed and operated by a handful of founders or one individual. The startup industry is an enormous part of the world's economy. Startups provide with thousands of new jobs assist in making up for jobs lost through automation and other traditional job losses. There are success and failures while many business fail and those that succeed will often make a splash through disrupting the industry. Country like India which is the 7th greatest nation by territory and the second most crowded nation with more than 1.2 billion individuals and it is notable that creating entrepreneurial aptitude among individuals is necessary and that they can't purely depend on employment and they can begin their own business. India has been ranked the 3rd biggest start up hub in the world and hence the Indian government has dispatched startup India to assist moving business visionaries.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The journey of entrepreneurs is lonely and without the support of ecosystem it's difficult to see the growth alone. The country has good techies. Handful of people want to work for startups as they are less paying in the initial days. The scope of entrepreneurship is very less due to the influence of mindset of the Indian families. They consider entrepreneurship as a bane. Some consider startups as chaos and some as sweatshops. The major issues discovered in Indian startups are the shifting priorities and dis satisfaction in raising funds. The investors stresses towards the generation of revenue and profitability and hence startups are under pressure for making money. The failure of culture, uneven hierarchy are also the major issues faced by startups. Hence in the current scenario the financing process of the startup hub is a relevant topic in today's business world.

OBJECTIVES

1. Understand the concept of Venture capital, Angel investors and Crowd funding.
2. How the growing startups are raising funds for their operations?
3. Challenges faced by startups and study the success rate.
4. Recent changes in startups.

RESEARCH QUESTION

“If every idea were to succeed, there would be no entrepreneurship”. The Indian entrepreneur are facing a problem of too much capital posing and it is quite a bit challenging for them in finding good use of the capital raised. Even though there is funding available for a few large companies and those which are in existing categories in general funding is still hard for the entrepreneurs. The question of whether premature stage entrepreneur should build the business for the long term or to sell and exit, there is always an argument that real entrepreneur doesn't build his company to sell and that he keeps it as a last choice. The research highlights the success rate of start up in India due to the funds raised through Venture capital, Angel investors and Crowd funding.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1) Prasad L (2017) - "kick- starting the startups- A case study." The conclusion states that even though there is a lot of issues, challenges and failures in the establishment of startups the availability of skilled technical man power, capital, incubation services, and government policies will lead them to a better place in the world by over taking established startup eco-system such as USA and UK.

2) Prinshak (2016) - "A study on crowd funding and its implications in India." Concluded that there will be requisite laws to support crowd funding as efficient crowd funding system can really play the role of catalyst in bringing the startup ideas to reality.

3) Prof Viren Chavda (2014) - topic name - The research work highlights the venture capital financing procedure which is followed globally, the different stages of growth of the firm and general overview of the venture capital funding in India. The results of his study is how India is promoting venture capital financing to new projects and the country still waits for the rapid venture capital funding business in India in spite of the existing challenges faced by the Indian industrial infrastructure.

4) Pallavi Rani, names, (2013) - " Venture capital: Growth and obstacles in India. Highlights the obstacles for venture capital funding and the development of various tools by venture capitalist to help optimise the entrepreneurs financing arrangements.

5) G.Usha-" Crowd funding for startups in India". The main attempt was to study about crowdfunding as a source of fund raising for startup. It also discuss about the guidelines given by SEBI for protecting the investors in India. Lastly it closes down by discussing the pros and cons of raising funds through crowd funding.

6) Harminder Singh, Manpreet kaur-" Startups in India- Retrospect and prospects". It highlights the early company life cycle, the current state of startups in India, the scope for its growth and challenges faced by them.

SCOPE

The youth of today seem to have a penchant for doing their own thing. Whether it is developing apps, starting their own design firms or even getting into manufacturing, India's youth wants something quite beyond the safety and security of government or corporate life. It is estimated that the number of start-ups in India will exceed 10000 by 2020 and this could well change how the labor market as well as the overall economy works in India. For existing investors also it provides scope. Investors in china began investing in earnest, putting money into 21 start ups as compared to just 12 in 2017. Investors from Japan (and not just soft bank) as well as other countries, also upped their funding in Indian startups.

METHODOLOGY

Keeping in view of availability of resources, the research paper is conducted on the basis of secondary sources of data. Secondary data has been collected from various online journals, research articles, case studies, conceptual studies, reports of various economic surveys etc.

DATA ANALYSIS

28 is the average age of start-up founders. In the year 2015 the estimated total funding for start-ups is \$5 billion. The number of start-ups in India is the third largest in the world after the US and UK, having 4,200-4,400 start-ups, and on an average there are 3-4 start-ups which are born every day, which has an average valuation of start-ups of \$2.5-2.7 million. It has 13-15% proportion of start-ups in E-commerce, which is the highest in any segment. It's successful in employing around 80,000-85,000 people in start-ups and creating job opportunities for plenty of people.

The number of mergers and acquisitions deals and exists involving start-ups seen in the 1st 3 quarters of 2015 is 65. The recent survey says the number of active angel investors in 2015-10-13 is 292.

Source: NASSCOM India and Zinnov consulting's start-up India report.

The impact of government's start-ups India and other initiatives on entrepreneurship in India has the following results.

- 1) Around 16% says it has helped a lot but could not be a better time to start-up
- 2) 60% says it has helped somewhat but not a significant catalyst.
- 3) 24% says the things are the same and red tape still exists.

Source: the economic times

DISCUSSION

Understanding the concept of:

Venture Capital- Firstly it is important to understand the term 'Venture Capitalist'. They are the investors who provide funds but don't provide business know-how, they don't help the business in finding the loopholes in the business model and improving them. They take money from big companies and invest in the startups which has potential for success and reshape markets and grow very fast. Venture capitalists take investments of big investors and provide the investment as funds to the startups. If there is a profit in the startup it is a beneficial aspect to the business men who made investment. Venture capital is a high- risk, high reward game that funds innovative ideas and keep the tech world going.

Features of Venture Capital

1. Form of equity participation: Venture capital is usually in the form of equity participation, it may also take the form of convertible debt or long term loan.
2. High Risk: Investment is made only in high risk and in high growth potential projects.
3. Only Commercialization of new ideas: Venture capital is generally for commercialization and not for enterprises which are engaged in trading, booking, financial services, research and development etc.

4. Joins entrepreneurs as co-promoters: venture capitalists joins the entrepreneurs as co-partners in the projects and share the risks and rewards of the enterprise.
5. Continuous process: Once the venture reaches its full potential the venture capitalist disinvests their holdings.
6. It's not just injection of money: It's not just injection of money but also an input needed to set up the firm, design its marketing strategy and organize and manage it.

Forms of Venture capital available in India are as follows.

1. Equity Participation: Venture Capital firms participate in equity through direct purchase of shares but their stake does not exceed 49% of the total equity capital. The control and majority of ownership of the business firms remain with the entrepreneurs.
2. Conventional Loan: Under this form a lower fixed rate of interest is charged till the assisted units become commercially operational, after which the loan carries normal or higher rate of interest. This loan is repayable in the form of royalty after generating sales.
3. Conditional Loan: Under this form of finance, an interest-free loan is provided and this loan is repayable in the form of royalty after generating sales.
4. Income notes: It is a combination of conventional and conditional loans where the features are combined. The entrepreneur has to pay both interest and royalty on sales but at a lower rate of interest.
5. At present, several venture capital firms are incorporated in India and they are promoted either by All India Financial Institutions like IDBI, ICICI, IFCI, Public sector banks or promoted by foreign banks/ private sector banks like Indus Venture Capital Fund.

Angel Investors- An angel investor is a person, business or group that provides financial backing for small start-ups or entrepreneur. Angel investors are usually found among the family and friends of the entrepreneurs. The capital they provide can be a one-time dose of seed money or continuing support to carry the company through difficult times. Angel investors can make investments on their own or as a part of a syndicate. Angel investors invest in early stage or start-up companies in exchange for an equity ownership interest. Angel investing in start-ups has been accelerating.

Angel investors particularly care about:

1. The quality, passion, commitment and integrity of the founders.
2. The market opportunity being addressed and the potential for the company to become very big.
3. A clearly thought out business plan and any early evidence of obtaining traction toward the plan.

Angel investors give more approving terms than other lenders, as they are usually investing in the person rather than the feasibility of the business. They are focussed on helping the business succeed, rather than reaping huge profit from their investment.

Crowd funding- As the name suggests crowd i.e. the people funds the business. It is the collection of funds from the crowd or people who likes the business. Crowd funding is the way for business to raise money in the form of donations or investment from multiple individuals. Crowd funding involves small companies raising funds from investors using the internet usually networking sites or crowd funding websites. The small amount of money which is obtained from a large number of individuals or firms to fund a project through an online web based platform.

Types of crowd funding in India:

Donation-based crowdfunding is a way to source money for a particular project by asking a huge number of contributors to donate a small amount to it. In return the investors may receive token rewards that increase in prestige as the size of the donation increases.

Reward based crowdfunding involves individuals contributing small amounts of money to projects in return for some kind of reward. The size of the reward is usually a part of the amount contributed.

Equity crowdfunding is the process whereby people invest in an early stage unlisted company. The shareholder has partial ownership of a company and stands to profit should the company do well.

Debt based crowdfunding- also known as peer to peer lending. Individuals lend money to businesses or other individuals with the expectation that it will be repaid with interest added.

Challenges and opportunities

Some of the Challenges faced by startups in India

1. Policies of the government: The role of the government in granting out loan has been limited. The startup thrive to succeed in the market, it is difficult to start any business in India as it involves a lot of laws and rules and regulations which the startup need to abide.

2. Mentoring: Starting a new venture or startup is a risky and often considered to be lonely journey for entrepreneurs. For startups finding a good mentor is a difficult task, the success or failure of a business depends on the mentors of the business and whole.

3 lack of planning and visualizing: An essential components of a startup culture is planning .often people take it lightly and forget to take into consideration important things like resources, budget, and potential risks it will face in future. Which will result sometimes in failure of the startups.

4 funding: Access to capital is one of the biggest problem for a startup.it is often a hectic task for the startup. It is often manic task for the startup to raise funds, as funding is a challenge and is done only up to the seed rounds by the financing investors, and a major part of role and management should be taken care of by the entrepreneurs themselves.

5. Dealing with competitors: Though the startup firm may have great product and services but when it comes to competition, the companies could be challenged to compete with their competitors. Mere raising of funds is not a success of a startup but the startup should have a great strategy by their side and adapt themselves to the latest trends in order to determine the position of the startup in the market.

Opportunities for startups in India

1. India's Population Has Opened New Gateways- The population of India is a huge asset for the country in the next few years. By 2020, it is supposed that the nation will be experiencing a "demographic bonus" period, where the working age population would surpass the non-working population.
2. Huge investment from Indian a foreign investors-The Indian startups are getting substantial support from foreign and Indian investors, who have been a great support to the Indian startups and they provide funds to help the companies in India to grow. There

has been an increase of more than 300 active angel investors, venture capital in the year 2015, the Indian startups had almost had raised around 423000 crores from various financing investors in the last year.

3. Government provides funds- Government of India has also been the biggest backbone where it funds the budding entrepreneurs in India. The government of India has helped the startup firm to perform nationally and in the international market. Where the government provides numerous assistance to the startups to grow in the market.
4. Make in India- The initiative started called make in India has encouraged the manufacturing and also the Indian buyers to trust and invest in the domestic startups in India.
5. Mudra yojna scheme- Getting loans and finance or to run a business by small entrepreneurs in India is very difficult. So the mudra yojna scheme helps the entrepreneurs to get loans from Banks and stabilize themselves and grow in the market.
6. SETU fund- The Self-Employment and Talent Utilization fund has been established by the government of India to help the startup firm's growth. The government has allowed 1000 crores program so that it helps them to create opportunities for entrepreneurs for self-employment and start new job.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Our research paper is based on secondary information only
2. It is just an overall study of the contribution of the investment agencies like venture capital, Angel investors and crowd funding towards the growth of the startups in the economy.
3. The study focuses only on the financing agencies like venture capital, Angel investors and crowd funding and not any other Investment agencies in financing the Indian startups.

SUGGESTIONS

- 1) Entrepreneurs should be motivated and has to test their ideas constantly. It is necessary to conduct proper analysis of each and every financial aspect.
- 2) It is required to stay focused in giving value to the customer.
- 3) Encouraging people to be passionate and diligent to start a new venture which involves risk taking and hence creating job opportunities to the greater good.
- 4) First generation entrepreneur has to focus on the important things in their venture and stop being depressed or getting annoyed.
- 5) Finance has to be handled with care. The entrepreneur has to forecast the business position for the next 5 years or so and take professional advice for investing.

FINDINGS

On an average the overall funding at the early stage (only seed and pre- series A stage) has dropped by 26% where is was 481.9 crore in 2017 and 297.1 crore till October 2018. The number of deals, average deal size and the drop in share of investments in pre-seed firm has reduced in 2018 when compared to 2017. The sector expected to continue getting investments in 2019 are consumers, enterprise tech, and artificial intelligence, health care and content.

Source: The Economic Times

CONCLUSION

The global markets are becoming more and more competitive. Financing start-ups which offers innovative products and services, technology venture has been a challenge in every economy. The paper explained the concepts like venture capital, Angel investors and Crowd funding which are opted by start-ups for funding their operations. It also discussed the challenges and opportunities faced by the Indian start-ups in comparison with USA and UK are discussed. Over a period of time from 2011 to 2013 there is a growth in the curve of Venture capital funding the start-ups, followed by Crowdfunding and lastly the Angel investors.

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